

Tetrad in Curved Space-Time in Cosmological General Theory of Relativity

Sangwha-Yi*

Department of Math, Taejon University 300-716, South Korea

*Corresponding Author: Sangwha-Yi, Department of Math, Taejon University 300-716, South Korea

Abstract: In the cosmological general theory of relativity, we define the tetrad that moves in r-axis in the curved space-time. We study an accelerated motion in curved space-time.

Keywords: Cosmological General Theory of Relativity; Tetrad in Curved Space-Time; Constant Accelerated Motion

PACS Number: 04,04.90.+e

1. INTRODUCTION

This theory's aim is to define tetrad that moves in r-axis in the curved space-time.

Schwarzschild solution is

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left[\frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

In this case, the cosmological time t_0 is the present cosmological time for constant accelerated motion in cosmological general theory of relativity [2,3]. The ratio of the universe's expansion is

$$\Omega(t_0) = 1 \quad (1-i)$$

Hence, in this time, the cosmological general theory of relativity and the cosmological special theory of relativity do the general relativity theory and the special relativity theory.

In this time, a moving matter's acceleration is the constant acceleration a_0 in the Schwarzschild space-time.

$$a_0 = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{u}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2} - \frac{u^2}{c^2}}} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$a_0 t = \frac{u}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2} - \frac{u^2}{c^2}}}, \quad u = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \frac{a_0 t}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}}} \quad (3)$$

If $\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{d\phi}{dt} = 0$, the solution is

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \quad (4)$$

In this time, if we use ψ ,

$$1 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) \left(\frac{dt}{d\tau}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \left(\frac{dr}{d\tau}\right)^2$$

$$\cosh \psi = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \frac{dt}{d\tau}, \quad \sinh \psi = \frac{1}{c} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}} \frac{dr}{d\tau} \quad (5)$$

Therefore, r-axis's velocity V_r is

$$V_r = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}} \frac{dr}{dt} = u = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \frac{a_0 t}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}}} \quad (6)$$

According to Eq(5),Eq(6),

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}} = \frac{1}{c} \frac{a_0 t}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} dt, \quad \cosh \psi = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \frac{dt}{d\tau}$$

$$= \frac{1}{c} \frac{a_0 t}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}}} \cosh \psi d\tau = \sinh \psi d\tau$$

$$\frac{1}{\cosh^2 \psi} = 1 - \left(\frac{\sinh \psi}{\cosh \psi}\right)^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{a_0 t/c}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}}}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}} \quad (7)$$

Hence,

$$\cosh \psi = \sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}}, \quad \sinh \psi = \frac{a_0 t}{c} \quad (8)$$

$$\cosh \psi = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \frac{dt}{d\tau} = \sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}}, \quad \sinh \psi = \frac{1}{c} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}} \frac{dr}{d\tau} = \frac{a_0 t}{c} \quad (9)$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{dt}{d\tau} = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}}, \quad \frac{1}{c} \frac{dr}{d\tau} = \frac{a_0 t}{c} \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \quad (10)$$

2. TETRAD IN CURVED SPACE-TIME

The tetrad e_a^μ is the unit vector that is each other orthographic.

$$e_a^\mu e_b^\nu g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{ab} \quad (11)$$

Therefore, Eq(11) is

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\mu\nu} e_0^\mu(r,t) e_0^\nu(r,t) &= \eta_{00} = -1 \\ d\tau^2 &= -\frac{1}{c^2} g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu \\ \rightarrow -1 &= g_{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau}\right) \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{dx^\nu}{d\tau}\right) = g_{\mu\nu} e_0^\mu(r,t) e_0^\nu(r,t) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

According to Eq(10),Eq(12)

$$\begin{aligned} e_0^\alpha(r,t) &= \frac{1}{c} \frac{dx^\alpha}{d\tau} \\ &= \left(\frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}}, \frac{a_0 t}{c} \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}, 0, 0 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

About θ -axis's and ϕ -axis's orientation

$$g_{22} e_2^2(r,t) e_2^2(r,t) = \eta_{22} = 1, \quad e_2^\alpha(r,t) = (0, 0, \frac{1}{r}, 0) \quad (14)$$

$$g_{33} e_3^3(r,t) e_3^3(r,t) = \eta_{33} = 1, \quad e_3^\alpha(r,t) = (0, 0, 1/r \sin\theta, 0) \quad (15)$$

And the other vector $e_1^\alpha(r,t)$ has to satisfy the tetrad condition, Eq (11)

$$\begin{aligned} g_{00} e_0^0(r,t) e_1^0(r,t) + g_{11} e_0^1(r,t) e_1^1(r,t) &= \eta_{01} = 0 \\ e_1^\alpha(r,t) &= \left(\frac{a_0 t/c}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}}, \sqrt{1 + \frac{a_0^2 t^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}, 0, 0 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

3. CONCLUSION

In the cosmological general theory of relativity, we define the tetrad that moves in r-axis in the curved space-time.

REFERENCES

- [1]S.Yi,"Curvature Tensor of the Stationary Accelerated Frame in Gravity Field", African Review of Physics,**9**,59,(2014)
- [2]S.Yi,"Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity", International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science,**7**,11,(2020),pp 4-9
- [3]S.Yi,"Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity", International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science,**8**,2,(2021),pp 22-26
- [4]S.Weinberg, Gravitation and Cosmology (John Wiley & Sons,Inc,1972)
- [5]P.Bergman, Introduction to the Theory of Relativity (Dover Pub. Co.,Inc., New York,1976),Chapter V
- [6]C.Misner, K,Thorne and J. Wheeler, Gravitation(W.H.Freedman & Co.,1973)
- [7]S.Hawking and G. Ellis,The Large Scale Structure of Space-Time(Cam-bridge University Press,1973)
- [8]R.Adler, M.Bazin and M.Schiffer, Introduction to General Relativity(McGraw-Hill,Inc.,1965)
- [9]M.Schwarzschild, Structure and Evolution of the Stars(Princeton University Press,1958;reprint,Dover,N.Y.1965),chapter II
- [10]S.Chandrasekhar, Mon,Not.Roy.Astron.Soc.95.207(1935)
- [11]C.Rhoades, "Investigations in the Physics of Neutron Stars", doctoral dissertation, Princeton University
- [12]J.Oppenheimer and H.Snyder, phys.Rev.56,455(1939)

Citation: Sangwha-Yi (2021). Tetrad in Curved Space-Time in Cosmological General Theory of Relativity. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science (IJARPS)* 8(4), pp.16-19, 2021.

Copyright: © 2021 Authors, This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.